

The Influence of Metal Impurities on NiOOH Electrocatalytic Activity in the Oxygen Evolution Reaction

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The energy transition and the implementation of new electrochemical technologies will result in an increased reliance on critical raw materials for electrodes. Their large-scale application will ultimately mean working with lower grade materials. Here we study the influence of metal impurities on nickel foam electrocatalysts. We do this by electrode depositing known amounts of first-row transition metals (Cu, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co and Ni) on nickel foam and studying their performance in the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) as a model reaction. The electrodes' performance is studied using cyclic voltammetry (CV), linear sweep voltammetry (LSV), Tafel analysis, stepwise

chronoamperometry (CA) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Combining these results with microscopy analysis, we show that even small amounts of transition-metal impurities have profound effects on the catalytic performance of nickel electrodes. The changes affect the OER onset potential (the energy that the system requires to convert OH⁻ to O₂) and the Tafel slope of each electrode (the electrode's initial activity in the OER onset region). Our results highlight the implications of such impurities on electrode design and future large-scale application.

Introduction

Whichever way you look at it, our world is changing. We are crossing more and more planetary boundaries.^[1–3] To minimise the effects of these transgressions, we must switch from fossil-carbon-based technologies to renewable ones, and replace our linear economy with a circular one. Large-scale production of clean electricity and the electrification of the transport, heating and chemical sectors are essential for this.^[4–10] Yet such large-scale operations incur challenges regarding materials and technologies. Today's small-scale applications of electrochemical devices use ultra-high-purity materials and well-defined reaction conditions. But as the applications grow across sectors and countries, more and more materials will have to be recycled and/or obtained from low-grade sources.

The critical raw materials (CRMs) list published by the European Commission includes not only platinum group metals (PGMs) but also cobalt, nickel, copper and manganese.^[11] Today, the EU imports these metals from a small and select group of

suppliers. The alternative, namely sourcing these metals from within Europe, is difficult. Recycling of CRMs is possible, but it would not cover the increasing demand. Additional sustainable mining within and outside Europe would still be needed. In the long term, both approaches would lead to an increase in impurities.

Ultimately, we seek a closed cycle operation, where all metals are recycled, and nothing goes to waste. But this also means working with less pure materials. For electrodes, this might mean anything from a few ppm to a few percent of impurities. Where large-scale operations are concerned, geography also plays a role. When multiple miners and manufacturers are utilised, the composition and type of impurities will reflect the starting materials and production processes at each location.^[12–16] Therefore, understanding how such impurities affect the catalytic performance of electrodes and electrochemical devices is crucial.

Here we study metal effects on an electrode's catalytic performance, using the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) as a model reaction. During alkaline OER, hydroxide is oxidised at the anode to molecular oxygen.^[17–19] For alkaline OER, three distinct mechanisms have been proposed: adsorbate evolution mechanism (AEM), intramolecular oxygen coupling (IMOC) and lattice oxygen mechanism (LOM).^[20] The four-step sequence shown below depicts the AEM mechanism (eqs 1–4, where * represents the electrode's active site and *OH, *O and *OOH represent the adsorbed species on the active site):

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We introduce metal impurities onto nickel foam electrodes by electrodeposition and study the effects on nickel activity in OER. We focus on the most common first-row transition metals (Cr, Mn, Fe, Co and Cu) as these are most likely to be present as impurities due to their similar ionic size, charge and abundance.^[12,13,21] By combining electrochemical measurements and material characterisation, we show that even small amounts of impurities at the surface can have large effects on the electrodes' performance. We discuss the implications of such impurities on electrode design and large-scale applications.

Importantly, our hypotheses are supported by analyses using both practical and fundamental methods. Conventionally, fundamental methods such as cyclic voltammetry (CV) and Tafel analysis are used to study electrode performance. However, these methods are less relevant during industrial electrolysis. Therefore, we also studied applied methods such as short term constant potential electrolysis. The comparison across different types of techniques holds the key to understanding the influence of lower purity electrodes under real-life operating conditions.

Results and Discussion

Electrode Synthesis and Configuration

Considering practical options, we chose to focus on nickel foam-based electrodes. Nickel is a relatively abundant metal with a high corrosion resistance.^[22,23] This makes it a good candidate for industrial electrocatalysis. To mimic the expected low-grade nickel in the future, we introduced impurities via

electrodeposition. This method is simple, fast, and scalable, giving good control over the electrode surface composition. In real-life situations, the impurities would enter the electrode in a different manner, yet these samples give us insight into the effects of the different metals on nickel activity.

Initially we looked at different procedures for cleaning nickel foam (NF). We found that the cleaning procedure strongly influences the deposition of transition metal (impurities) on the electrode. As an example, let us consider the cathodic deposition of copper on NF. Electrodes cleaned with different procedures and plated from different concentration baths showed varied copper deposition morphologies (see optical microscopy images in Figure 1). In a typical preparation, 2 mg of metal species were electrodeposited from a low concentration plating bath on a pre-cleaned piece of nickel foam. The foam was cleaned by sequential washing in hydrochloric acid, acetone, ethanol and ultrapure water (see experimental section for detailed procedures). Although one would expect that cathodic deposition results in M^0 particles, we saw in some cases the formation of oxides (see below).

Figure 1 A and B show the cleaned nickel foam at 50x and 500x magnification. The optical microscopy images give a hands-on view of the foam electrodes and the deposition of the metal impurities thereupon. The surface is smooth, shiny and silver coloured. Figure 1 C shows electrodeposited copper on nickel foam from a high concentration plating bath (0.1 M). Here we see that the surface is partially covered with metallic copper particles as well as large red translucent octahedral crystals, about 20 microns across. The specific shape and colour of these crystals implies that this is cuprous oxide (Cu_2O).^[24–26] Figure 1 D, E and F show the nickel foam with electrodeposited copper from a low concentration plating bath (0.01 M) at 50x

Figure 1. Optical microscopy photos of the nickel foam electrodes; (a) bare NF at 50x magnification; (b) bare NF 500x magnification. (c) Cu/NF plated using a high concentration bath (0.1 M) at 500x magnification showing large translucent red octahedral Cu_2O crystals. (d) Cu/NF plated using a low concentration bath (0.01 M) at 50x magnification. (e, f) Cu/NF plated using a low concentration bath (0.01 M) at 500x magnification showing more metallic or oxidised plating depending on the position of the electrode. Deposition was performed at 50 °C in a non-separated cell using a two-electrode setup with a Ti mesh Ir-MMO coated counter electrode.

and 500x magnification. Depending on the position on the electrode, we can see more metallic or oxidised plated copper.

Plating Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, and Ni on nickel foam (the latter used as a blank for evaluating the plating process) yielded less defined morphologies (Figure 2). On the chromium electrode we see white/greenish crystals. Mn/NF has a reddish-brown colour, but no crystal formation. Iron is deposited as a blackened, matt silvery coating with occasional reddish-brown areas. These areas are most likely rust, Fe_2O_3 , as small iron particles readily oxidize in air. The cobalt-plated electrode has a similar shiny silvery look as the pristine nickel foam. Higher magnification, however, reveals small spherical particles on the surface. Finally, the Ni/NF electrode shows a similar surface

roughness as the original nickel foam, but the colour is blackened. Note that in all cases the surface is not fully covered by the electrodeposited metals, with patches of bare nickel foam.

Performance Studies

We then compared the catalytic performance of the plated electrodes using the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) as a benchmark. Nickel is a commonly used metal for electrochemical oxidations in alkaline environment,^[27–32] and OER can tell us much about the electrodes' function. To understand the

Figure 2. Optical microscopy photos of Cr/NF at 50x (a1) and 500x (a2) magnification showing deposition of white/greenish crystals; Mn/NF at 50x (b1) and 500x (b2) magnification showing a reddish-brown compound deposition; Fe/NF at 50x (c1) and 500x (c2) magnification is deposited as a blackened, matt silvery coating with occasional rust formation; Co/NF at 50x (d1) and 500x (d2) magnification showing small spherical particles on the surface; Ni/NF at 50x (e1) and 500x (e2) magnification is slightly blackened; and bare NF at 50x (f1) and 500x (f2) magnification having a shiny silvery and smooth surface. The metal loading varies between 1.8–2.4 mg. Deposition was performed at 50 °C and $-6 \text{ mA/cm}^2_{\text{geo}}$ in a non-separated cell using a two-electrode setup with a Ti mesh Ir-MMO coated counter electrode and a plating bath concentration of 0.01 M.

influence of the different transition metals on the nickel oxyhydroxide phase in OER, we studied first the bare clean nickel foam electrode. We ran cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements in alkaline media in a separated cell (Figure 3, for details see experimental section). We see two events between 0.1 V vs. SCE and 0.45 V vs. SCE. When the metallic nickel foam is in contact with the alkaline electrolyte, a chemical reaction takes place and the surface is oxidised to $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$.^[33,34] When an oxidative potential is applied, this nickel hydroxide is converted to nickel oxyhydroxide.^[35–38] On the reverse scan of the CV, NiOOH is reduced back to $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$. The two events relate to the different phases of the oxidised nickel. There are two phases of nickel hydroxide, $\alpha\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\beta\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$. Nickel oxyhydroxide also has two phases, $\beta\text{-NiOOH}$ and $\gamma\text{-NiOOH}$. Phase transitions between all four species occur (electro)chemically

Figure 3. Cyclic voltammogram of the nickel redox couple of bare NF in 1 M KOH. (a) $\beta\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ is oxidised to $\beta\text{-NiOOH}$; (b) $\alpha\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ is oxidised to $\gamma\text{-NiOOH}$. The reverse scan shows the reductions of (c) $\gamma\text{-NiOOH}$ to $\alpha\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ and (d) $\beta\text{-NiOOH}$ to $\beta\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$. CVs were taken from 0 V vs SCE to 0.45 V vs SCE at 5 mV/sec, using a separated cell with a Fumasep FAA-3–50 membrane, a platinum counter electrode and a saturated calomel reference electrode.

Scheme 1. Bode diagram showing the transitions between the different nickel hydroxide and oxyhydroxide species (water molecules omitted for clarity).

(Scheme 1).^[27,39,40] When $\alpha\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ is aged in alkaline media it is converted to $\beta\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$. The $\beta\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ forms a redox couple with $\beta\text{-NiOOH}$. When $\beta\text{-NiOOH}$ is overcharged, it is converted to $\gamma\text{-NiOOH}$. Finally, $\gamma\text{-NiOOH}$ forms a redox couple with $\alpha\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$. Indeed, we see that all four species are present (two redox couples in the CV). The first couple is between $\beta\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\beta\text{-NiOOH}$ (a/d) and the second is between $\alpha\text{-Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\gamma\text{-NiOOH}$ (b/c). An alternative interpretation of the $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{III}}$ redox couple, mentions the effect of dissolved nickel species causing a shift in the peak position.^[41]

Comparing the CVs of the plated nickel foam electrodes in the nickel redox region (Figure 4) with those of the bare NF shows two distinct changes in electrochemical behaviour. The first difference is in the amount of active species. The area under the $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{Ni}^{3+}$ oxidation signals is lower for the plated electrodes (Table 1, integrated CVs are in Figure S1). This implies that the electrodeposition has partially covered the nickel foam

Figure 4. (a) Cyclic voltammogram of the plated electrodes and bare NF in 1 M KOH. A separated cell with a Fumasep FAA-3–50 membrane, a platinum counter electrode and a saturated calomel reference electrode were used. CVs were taken from 0 V vs SCE to 0.45 V vs SCE at 5 mV/sec. Compared to NF, the $\text{Ni}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Ni}^{3+}$ oxidation peak is shifted and flattened. This implies that the plated metals have an influence on the nickel species at the surface and that we are looking at nickel activity. (b) Integration of the nickel oxidation peak of bare nickel foam showing the amount of active nickel species ($Q/\text{cm}^2_{\text{geo}}$).

Table 1. Equivalents of active species on the electrodes' surfaces based on charge per surface area.		
Entry	Electrode	Q/cm ² _{geo}
1	NF	0.085
2	Cu/NF	0.035
3	Ni/NF	0.063
4	Co/NF	0.062
5	Fe/NF	0.022
6	Mn/NF	0.054
7	Cr/NF	0.069

surface. Such a coverage likely occurs at the most active spots (as these, per definition, would be the higher energy sites and therefore would release more energy when coated). But as electrochemistry takes place at the surface, we know that the nickel foam support is still exposed to the electrolyte as the redox couple is still present. The Pourbaix diagrams of the plated metals as well as reported electrodes in literature, confirm that this oxidation potential window pertains to nickel.^[42–46] Additionally, these metals can incorporate into the NiOOH structure. Iron incorporation into the NiOOH phase is most commonly known and has been studied by Jian-Bo He and coworkers amongst others.^[47] It has been shown that manganese and cobalt can incorporate into the nickel phase as well.^[48–50] The second change we see is in the position of the oxidation peaks. For the plated electrodes, the onset potential for converting nickel hydroxide to nickel oxyhydroxide is shifted to either higher or lower potentials depending on the metal deposited (likely, the lower activity of Ni/NF compared to pristine NF reflects the fact that the “new” nickel particles occupy high-energy sites that were responsible for activity of the pristine electrode). This shows that depositing even small amounts of transition metals influences the energy required to oxidise the nickel hydroxide to nickel oxyhydroxide.

To observe the oxygen evolution reaction, cyclic voltammetry experiments must be run at higher potentials. Figure 5 shows a CV running up to 0.8 V vs SCE. In this CV we can see the Ni²⁺ → Ni³⁺ oxidation between 0.3 and 0.4 V vs SCE, while the OER takes place from 0.44 V vs SCE. On the reverse scan we see the reduction of Ni³⁺ → Ni²⁺ between 0.3 and 0.2 V vs SCE. To minimise mass transfer limitations, the CV experiment was stirred at 250 rpm (the effect of the magnetic stirring is also observed, as the data becomes a little noisier).

Again, comparing the plated electrodes to the plain nickel foam, we see a few differences (Figure 6). First, the plated electrodes show a lower signal for the nickel transition than the bare NF. This is because (i) nickel active sites have been covered by transition metals, and (ii) the scan speed of 20 mV/s is too fast for the bare NF system to read out the stabilised current. Second, the OER starts at a lower potential for Fe, Cr and Mn on NF, whereas the reaction takes place at a higher potential for Cu/NF. The Co/NF and Ni/NF electrodes have a similar onset potential as bare NF. Third, when compared to the bare NF, only the copper-plated electrode reaches a lower final current

Figure 5. Cyclic voltammogram of bare NF in 1 M KOH. CVs were measured at room temperature from 0 to 0.8 V vs SCE at a scan speed of 20 mV/sec while stirring, using a separated cell with a Fumasep FAA-3–50 membrane, a platinum counter electrode and a saturated calomel reference electrode. On the oxidative scan, Ni²⁺ → Ni³⁺ oxidation is seen between 0.30 and 0.35 V vs. SCE followed by OER starting from 0.48 V vs. SCE. On the reductive scan, Ni³⁺ → Ni²⁺ reduction takes place between 0.3 and 0.2 V vs. SCE.

Figure 6. Cyclic voltammograms of the plated electrodes and bare NF in 1 M KOH. CVs were measured at room temperature from 0 to 0.8 V vs SCE at 20 mV/sec while stirring, using a separated cell with a Fumasep FAA-3–50 membrane, a platinum counter electrode and a saturated calomel reference electrode. The stirring of the electrolyte while measuring the CVs resulted in noise in the data. The nickel redox couple is seen for all electrodes between 0.2 and 0.4 V vs. SCE. The OER onset potentials and final current densities reached are different for all electrodes with Fe/NF having the lowest and Cu/NF the highest.

density. Interestingly, we also see that Fe/NF reaches the highest current density, in agreement with published findings where Fe-NiOOH was shown to be the best-performing OER catalyst.^[39,51–53]

Unfortunately, the nickel redox couple overlaps with the OER onset for some of the plated electrodes. This results in unreliable Tafel slope calculations for initial reaction activity, as we don't have a clean baseline. To minimise the influence of the nickel redox couple, we followed the procedure reported by van der Heijden *et al.*^[54] We first ran a CV oxidising Ni²⁺ → Ni³⁺, stopping when this oxidation was complete. Then, we ran an oxidative linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) measurement, starting from the onset potential for Ni²⁺ oxidation. This avoids

nickel reduction, and since all the nickel has already been oxidised to Ni^{3+} , it removes any contribution of the nickel oxidation from the baseline (Figure 7). We performed the same baseline correction for all electrodes prior to measuring the LSVs. To ensure that our reactions are in the chemical rather than in the mass-transfer regime, we ran all the LSVs as both stirred and unstirred experiments. The results confirmed that there are no mass-transfer effects (see Figures S2 and S3). For clarity, we present the unstirred LSVs as these are less noisy (Figure 8).

The one exception is the CV of the bare NF. For this electrode, catalytic performance increases the longer the electrode is exposed to the alkaline electrolyte, even without applying any potential. Whereas the active nickel hydroxide/oxyhydroxide sites on the Ni/NF electrode have been covered

Figure 7. Linear sweep voltammogram of bare NF in 1 M KOH. LSV was measured at room temperature from 0.3 to 0.8 V vs SCE without stirring, using a separated cell with a Fumasep FAA-3–50 membrane, a platinum counter electrode and a saturated calomel reference electrode. Before performing the LSV the nickel oxidation signal was minimised. OER starts from 0.48 V vs. SCE.

Figure 8. Linear sweep voltammograms of the plated electrodes and bare nickel foam in 1 M KOH. LSVs were measured at room temperature from 0.3 to 0.8 V vs SCE without stirring, using a separated cell with a Fumasep FAA-3–50 membrane, a platinum counter electrode and a saturated calomel reference electrode. Before performing the LSV the nickel oxidation signal was minimised. The OER onset potentials and final current densities reached are different for all electrodes with Fe/NF having the lowest and Cu/NF the highest.

by less active species, this is not the case for the bare NF electrode. We hypothesise that exposing the electrode to the alkaline environment increases the number active nickel hydroxide/oxyhydroxide sites over time. Indeed, when we ran long-duration CVs, we also saw an increase in the final current density, just like in the LSV for this electrode.

Now that the nickel redox contribution is minimised, we could make Tafel plots from the LSVs and calculate the Tafel slopes. Tafel analysis is used to study the catalytic activity of an electrode. In a Tafel plot, the logarithmic current density is plotted in the onset potential region of the voltammogram. For Tafel analysis, we use only the linear part of such a plot. To compare the activity of different electrodes, the Tafel slope is calculated for this linear region. Electrodes with a low slope value are more active (a small increase in the applied potential translates to a large increase of the current density). The Tafel plots (Figure 9) confirm that the onset potentials of Fe/NF, Mn/NF and Cr/NF are the lowest from all the electrodes, with very similar values. The onset potentials of Ni/NF, Co/NF and plain NF are similar. Copper stands out here, as the Cu/NF electrode shows the highest OER onset potential *and* the highest Tafel slope value. This electrode is the least active with 106.58 mV/dec, followed by Ni/NF with 93.76 mV/dec and Co/NF at 75.08 mV/dec. These three electrodes are less active than bare NF, which has a Tafel slope of 66.93 mV/dec. Conversely, the manganese, iron and chromium electrodes are more active than bare NF. Of these, Mn/NF has the highest slope of 63.38 mV/dec, followed by Fe/NF at 56.53 mV/dec and finally Cr/NF with 54.22 mV/dec. This electrocatalyst has the highest activity near the equilibrium potential.

To rank the performance of the electrocatalysts, we plotted the Tafel slopes against the onset potentials (Figure 10). In this figure, electrodes in the top right corner have both high a Tafel slope and a high onset potential. This means that it takes more energy for the reaction to start (high onset potential) and when it does start, it is slow (high Tafel slope). Conversely, the electrodes at the bottom left require less energy for OER *and*

Figure 9. Tafel plots derived from LSV data of all electrodes with the Tafel slope indicated per electrode. Cu/NF has the highest Tafel slope (106.58 mV/dec) making it the slowest OER electrocatalyst near onset potential. Cr/NF has the lowest Tafel slope (54.22 mV/dec) making it the fastest OER electrocatalyst near onset potential.

Figure 10. Tafel slopes of all electrodes plotted against their OER onset potentials for performance ranking. The plated electrodes, show the classic split between early and late transition metals. Circled in blue, Fe/NF, Cr/NF and Mn/NF (early TMs) show the best performance for OER with Fe/NF being superior. The late transition metals (Co, Ni, Cu) are ranked according to their number of d-electrons going from iron to copper. Cu/NF has both the highest Tafel slope and highest onset potential, making it the worst OER electrocatalyst of this set.

give a faster reaction. We see that Cu/NF is in the top right quadrant, and indeed this electrode is the worst performing in OER. At the bottom left we find the iron, manganese and chromium electrodes clustered together. These three electrodes are highly similar and the best performing OER electrocatalysts. The remaining electrodes all have similar onset potentials but differ in their Tafel slope values.

Leaving out the bare NF support, we see a trend relating to the nature of the deposited transition metals. Copper, which has the highest number of d-electrons and therefore the highest electronegativity, shows the lowest performance. The plated nickel electrode is next, as it requires less energy to perform the OER, but is rather slow at it. Then we move on to the cobalt electrode, which has a much lower Tafel slope. The activity of these three electrodes is correlated with the number of valence d-electrons. Another similarity is that all three metals can lose up to two electrons each. Our data shows the classic split between earlier (Cr, Mn, Fe) and later (Co, Ni, Cu) transition metals. We find that Sabatier's optimum is reached with the iron-plated nickel foam electrode. The performance decreases for manganese and further for chromium.

LSV Data Validation with Chronoamperometry

To validate the current readout of the LSV measurements and gain insight into the electrodes' performance under industrially relevant conditions, we ran stepwise chronoamperometry (CA) experiments. In electrochemical experiments such as CV or LSV, the surface of the electrode is charged and a reactant concentration gradient forms between the electrode interface and diffuse layer.^[55] When performing electrochemical experiments, the initial reactant concentration near the electrodes' surface is higher than in the steady-state. The time needed for

reaching the steady-state concentration differs for every electrode according to its electron transfer ability. This initial high concentration at the surface results in a current "spike" early in the experiments. Good catalysts promote electron transfer, reaching the steady-state faster, and *vice versa*. The amount of time that is available for the system to reach the steady state in CV or LSV depends on the scan speed. Slow scanning gives the system more time to equilibrate. If the system has sufficient time to reach the steady state, the current readout will be accurate. Otherwise, the observed current will be too high.

For our CA experiments, we hold a potential starting from 400 mV vs SCE for 60 s before increasing the potential by 50 mV. We do this until we reach a final potential of 800 mV vs SCE (see example in Figure 11, all other CA data is shown in Figure S4). For the bare NF, electron transfer is fast. We know this because the plateaus are straight lines. When equilibration is slower, a peak is observed at the beginning of the CA measurement at a new potential (cf. the measurements at 500, 600, 700 and 800 mV vs SCE). The early data shows a slightly higher current readout than the rest of the experiment. At 800 mV vs SCE, the plateau signal is noisy, as a lot of oxygen is being produced at this potential. When a bubble forms on the surface, it shields the electrode from the electrolyte, increasing the resistance and resulting in a lower current readout. When the bubble leaves the surface, the current increases as more of the electrode is exposed.

To check if the LSV data overlaps with the CA data, we plotted the average current of the last 30 s of each CA step on the LSV curves (Figure 12). We see that the two currents, *measured using two different methods*, give a near-perfect match in all cases. This independent validation emphasises the accuracy and viability of our data. The one outlier is Cu/NF. Here the CA current is significantly lower than that observed with LSV. This means that the reaching the steady-state concentration is slow and that the current readout early on is

Figure 11. Chronoamperometry experiments showing the data used for the LSV calculations from a steady-state system. Conditions: room temperature, 400 to 800 mV vs. SCE with steps of 50 mV, using a separated cell with a Fumasep FAA-3-50 membrane, a platinum counter electrode and a saturated calomel reference electrode. Each potential was held for 1 min to allow the system to reach steady state. Signal is noisier at higher potentials due to vigorous oxygen generation at the electrode surface.

Figure 12. Linear sweep voltammograms and averaged chronoamperometry current density for all plated electrodes and bare NF. The second half of the CA data was averaged and is depicted as a single datapoint per potential. The CA data traces the LSVs for all electrodes, except for Cu/NF where the performance is lower.

too high. We can confirm this with the CA data of the copper electrode itself, where at higher potentials the stabilised current is much lower than the initial current. Indeed, the actual performance of the copper electrode is much lower than the LSV data implies. This is likely caused by the build-up of non-conductive cuprous oxide crystals on the surface (see microscopy images above).

As the overlap between the LSV and CA data is near perfect, we performed Tafel analysis on the CA data (Figure 13). In the Tafel plots two distinct regions are identified, region 1 at lower potentials where catalyst performance dominates and region 2 at higher potentials where migration and diffusion dominate. The shift from region 1 to 2 relates to the electrodes' performance. Electrodes with a high performance (Cr, Fe, Mn/NF) experience the shift at earlier potentials, in this case at 500 mV

Figure 13. Tafel plots derived from CA data for all electrodes. Two distinct regions are indicated for a lower and higher potential range. In region 1, where catalyst performance dominates, Cu/NF has the highest Tafel slope and Cr/NF has the lowest. The same trend is observed in this region compared to the Tafel analysis derived from LSV data. The shift to the region 2, where migration and diffusion dominate, relates to the performance of the electrode. Cu/NF shifts at 600 mV vs. SCE, Co Ni and NF at 550 mV vs. SCE and Mn Cr Fe/NF at 500 mV. SCE.

Entry	Electrode	Region 1 (mV/dec)	Region 2 (mV/dec)
1	NF	55.75	400.89
2	Cu/NF	93.33	332.77
3	Ni/NF	73.32	329.4
4	Co/NF	59.85	333.34
5	Fe/NF	48.85	196.6*
6	Mn/NF	49.51	349.31
7	Cr/NF	41.62	332.75

* Slope value calculated based on two data points only.

vs. SCE. Cu/NF, the least performing electrode shifts the latest at 600 mV vs. SCE. Electrodes with activities similar to bare NF move from region 1 to 2 at 550 mV vs. SCE. Table 2 shows the Tafel slopes for all electrodes in both regions. In region 1, the Tafel slopes slightly lower value compared to the values obtained from LSV data, but the exact same order is found even though the amount of datapoints is rather low. This shows that electrolysis data can be used as a tool to find fundamental descriptors for electrodes while using applied techniques. In region 2 the Tafel slopes are much higher for all electrodes, and they are comparable. This confirms that the catalyst performance is not the dominating factor, and that migration and diffusion effects are comparable between the electrodes resulting in similar Tafel slopes.

Reaction Resistance and Catalyst Performance

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) can tell us about the resistance of the physical system components as well as the resistance of the chemical reaction. Figure 14 shows the EIS results at 600 mV vs. SCE for all the electrodes. An equivalent circuit and data fitting is shown in Figures S5–12. The potential chosen for EIS should always be high enough for the desired reaction to take place. We see that the resistance of the system itself is very low in all cases, ranging from 0.15 ohms for Fe/NF to 0.35 ohms for Ni/NF. In this figure, the semicircles represent a reaction taking place at the set potential (OER in this case). The resistance of the electrochemical reaction is the absolute difference between the start and end of each semicircle. For Cu/NF this number is highest at 3.05 ohms. Fe/NF shows the smallest reaction resistance (better OER performance) at 0.05 ohms.

Figure 15 shows both the reaction resistances and the stable current density for CA at 600 mV vs SCE. We see that electrodes with a high stable current density (iron, chromium and manganese on NF) have a low reaction resistance. Additionally, we see that Cu/NF, the electrode with the highest reaction resistance, has the lowest stable current density. The two metrics should correlate, as a high resistance means the reaction is more difficult to perform, resulting in a lower current density. In Figure 15 we see this trend when we rank the

Figure 14. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy plots of all electrodes taken in 1 M KOH at 600 mV vs. SCE, in a separated cell equipped with a Fumasep FAA-3-50 membrane. The resistance of the system itself for all cases is very low (≤ 0.35 ohm). The reaction resistance of Cu/NF is highest at 3.05 ohm, whereas Fe/NF has the lowest at 0.05 ohm.

Figure 15. Comparison between the reaction resistance and current density for all electrodes in at 600 mV vs. SCE. The electrodes have been ranked from highest current density output to lowest, with NF as a control on the left.

electrodes by activity. As the current density decreases from iron to copper, the reaction resistance goes up. The fact that we measure this using two independent methods again emphasises the reliability of our data.

Conclusions

Small amounts of transition-metal impurities have profound effects on the electrocatalytic performance of nickel. The changes affect the OER onset potential (the energy that the system requires to convert OH^- to O_2), the Tafel slope (the electrode's initial activity in the OER onset region) and the parameters that govern electrolysis activity. These changes occur even when the impurity covers only a fraction of the electrode's surface. This means that the impurities interact with the original active sites on the nickel electrode. The electrodes show two distinct performance regions, at low and high potentials, reflecting the dominance of electrocatalysis and

migration/diffusion, respectively. Independent impedance and current density analyses show that the reactions' resistance per electrode is anti-correlated with the final current density output. On the methodological side, we show that measurement techniques used for fundamental studies (CV, LSV) and those used at industrial conditions (electrolysis) yield the same trends over the entire set of electrodes, despite the paucity of electrolysis data.

Experimental Section

Materials and Instrumentation

Unless noted otherwise, all chemicals were purchased from commercial sources and used as received. Nickel foam (99.99%) was obtained from Nanografi Nanotechnology. Acetone was obtained from VWR International. Hydrochloric acid (37%), ethanol absolute (99.8%), sulphuric acid (95.0 – 98.0%), boric acid (> 99.5%), nickel sulphate hexahydrate (> 99%), cobalt sulphate heptahydrate (> 99%), copper sulphate pentahydrate (> 99%), and chromium sulphate hydrate were obtained from Merck Sigma-Aldrich. Iron sulphate heptahydrate (> 99%) and manganese sulphate monohydrate (> 99%) were obtained from Honeywell Fluka. All solutions in this work were made using Millipore Milli-Q purified water. Unless stated otherwise, reactions were performed at ambient temperature and pressure. Electrochemical experiments were carried out using a Gamry Instruments reference 600 potentiostat. Specifically, electrode synthesis was performed in a single-compartment two-electrode cell. A Ti mesh Ir-MMO electrode was used as the counter. All other electrochemical measurements were carried out in non-purified 1 M KOH, in a separated cell equipped with a Fumasep FAA-3-50 anion exchange membrane and a Pt gauze (99.9%, Alfa Aesar) counter electrode. The electrolyte was replaced with fresh non-purified 1 M KOH between experiments and electrodes. For consistency and comparability, KOH was taken from a stock solution. For the three-electrode systems, the potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE, Gamry Instruments). Optical microscope images were taken on a Delphi-X Observer using a sCMEX-20 camera with ImageFocusAlpha software.

Procedures

Electrode Synthesis

Nickel foam (NF) was cut into 1×2 cm pieces and the top half was flattened to give an active geometrical area of 1 cm². To prepare the foam for electrochemical experiments, the surface was cleaned by sonication in 4 M HCl for 30 minutes. Afterwards the foam was sequentially washed by sonicated in acetone, absolute EtOH, and water for 15 minutes. In between each washing step the NF pieces were rinsed with water. The cleaned NF was dried overnight at room temperature. Teflon tape was added to the interface between the active area and the flattened excess.

Electroplating baths were prepared by dissolving 0.01 M transition metal (TM) precursor sulphate salt and boric acid (15 g/L) in water. The bath's pH was brought to 3.5 by addition of sulphuric acid. With a two-electrode setup, 1 mg/cm²_{geo} of TM was deposited on the cleaned NF at −0.6 mA/cm²_{geo} at 50 °C. After electrodeposition, the electrodes were washed with water and dried overnight at room temperature.

Cyclic Voltammetry (CV)

Before starting CV measurements, the working compartment was stirred for 8 min at 250 rpm. The first round of CVs was taken within the Ni^{2+/3+} transition window of 0 to 0.45 V vs. SCE. At scan speeds of 100, 50, 20 and 5 mV/s, 3 cycles were run. The uncompensated resistance (R_u) was measured at 0.45 V vs. SCE before CVs were taken of the oxygen evolution reaction (OER). Again, 3 cycles were taken but for OER, CVs were run from 0 to 0.8 V vs. SCE at a scan speed of 20 mV/s while stirring the electrolyte at 250 rpm. Afterwards, the R_u was taken at 0.7 V vs. SCE.

Linear Sweep Voltammetry (LSV)

To remove any contribution of the Ni^{2+/3+} transition to the OER onset region, the CV runs were ended at the oxidative upper limit. LSVs were taken from 0.3 to 0.8 V vs. SCE at a scan speed of 20 mV/s. This was performed first stirred and then in unstirred electrolyte.

Chronoamperometry (CA)

CA experiments were carried out stepwise over a range of potentials. Starting from 0.4 V vs. SCE and with steps of 50 mV, a potential was held for 60 seconds until the final potential, 0.8 V vs. SCE was reached.

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

After stirring the working electrolyte for 5 minutes, EIS measurements were carried out at 0.6 V vs. SCE at frequencies ranging from 1·10⁶ to 0.1 Hz.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: electrocatalysis · electrification · surface impurities · cyclic voltammetry · electrodeposition

- [1] J. Rockström, W. Steffen, K. Noone, Å. Persson, F. S. Chapin, E. F. Lambin, T. M. Lenton, M. Scheffer, C. Folke, H. J. Schellnhuber, B. Nykvist, C. A. de Wit, T. Hughes, S. van der Leeuw, H. Rodhe, S. Sörlin, P. K. Snyder, R. Costanza, U. Svedin, M. Falkenmark, L. Karlberg, R. W. Corell, V. J. Fabry, J. Hansen, B. Walker, D. Liverman, K. Richardson, P. Crutzen, J. A. Foley, *Nature* **2009**, *461*, 472–475.
- [2] W. Steffen, K. Richardson, J. Rockström, S. E. Cornell, I. Fetzer, E. M. Bennett, R. Biggs, S. R. Carpenter, W. de Vries, C. A. de Wit, C. Folke, D. Gerten, J. Heinke, G. M. Mace, L. M. Persson, V. Ramanathan, B. Reyers, S. Sörlin, *Science* **2015**, *347*, 1259855.
- [3] K. Richardson, W. Steffen, W. Lucht, J. Bendtsen, S. E. Cornell, J. F. Donges, M. Drüke, I. Fetzer, G. Bala, W. von Bloh, G. Feulner, S. Fiedler, D. Gerten, T. Gleeson, M. Hofmann, W. Huiskamp, M. Kumm, C. Mohan, D. Nogués-Bravo, S. Petri, M. Porkka, S. Rahmstorf, S. Schaphoff, K. Thonicke, A. Tobian, V. Virkki, L. Wang-Erlandsson, L. Weber, J. Rockström, *Sci. Adv.* **2023**, *9*, eadh2458.
- [4] D. F. Dominković, I. Bačeković, A. S. Pedersen, G. Krajačić, *Renewable Sustainable Energy Rev.* **2018**, *82*, 1823–1838.
- [5] T. Galimova, M. Ram, D. Bogdanov, M. Fasihi, A. Gulagi, S. Khalili, C. Breyer, *Renewable Sustainable Energy Rev.* **2023**, *183*, 113420.
- [6] M. Yuan, J. Z. Thellufsen, H. Lund, Y. Liang, *Energy* **2021**, *236*, 121564.
- [7] D. Bogdanov, M. Ram, A. Aghahosseini, A. Gulagi, A. S. Oyewo, M. Child, U. Caldera, K. Sadovskaia, J. Farfan, L. De Souza Noel Simas Barbosa, M. Fasihi, S. Khalili, T. Traber, C. Breyer, *Energy* **2021**, *227*, 120467.
- [8] I. Eryazici, N. Ramesh, C. Villa, *MRS Bull.* **2021**, *46*, 1197–1204.
- [9] K. M. Van Geem, B. M. Weckhuysen, *MRS Bull.* **2021**, *46*, 1187–1196.
- [10] R. Zhang, S. Fujimori, *Environ. Res. Lett.* **2020**, *15*, 034019.
- [11] European Commission, Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, M. Grohol, C. Veeh, *Study on the Critical Raw Materials for the EU 2023: Final Report*, Publications Office Of The European Union, LU, **2023**.
- [12] S. Farrokhpay, L. Filippov, D. Fornasiero, *Miner. Eng.* **2019**, *141*, 105892.
- [13] G. Bartzas, K. Komnitsas, *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **2015**, *105*, 113–122.
- [14] S. J. Barnes, R. E. T. Hill, C. S. Perring, S. E. Dowling, *Mineral. Petrol.* **2004**, *82*, 259–293.
- [15] G. M. Mudd, *Ore Geol. Rev.* **2010**, *38*, 9–26.
- [16] D. M. Hoatson, S. Jaireth, A. L. Jaques, *Ore Geol. Rev.* **2006**, *29*, 177–241.
- [17] Q. Liang, G. Brocks, A. Bieberle-Hütter, *J. Phys. E* **2021**, *3*, 026001.
- [18] F. Lu, M. Zhou, Y. Zhou, X. Zeng, *Small* **2017**, *13*, 1701931.
- [19] A. Alobaid, C. Wang, R. A. Adomaitis, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2018**, *165*, J3395.
- [20] Z. Wang, W. A. Goddard, H. Xiao, *Nat. Commun.* **2023**, *14*, 4228.
- [21] Y. Li, V. G. Papangelakis, I. Perederiy, *Hydrometallurgy* **2009**, *97*, 185–193.
- [22] C. A. C. Sequeira, D. S. P. Cardoso, L. Amaral, B. Šljukić, D. M. F. Santos, *Corros. Rev.* **2016**, *34*, 187–200.
- [23] P. Chirik, R. Morris, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2015**, *48*, 2495–2495.
- [24] C. Leygraf, T. Chang, G. Herting, I. Odnevall Wallinder, *Corros. Rev.* **2019**, *157*, 337–346.
- [25] W. Zhao, W. Fu, H. Yang, C. Tian, M. Li, Y. Li, L. Zhang, Y. Sui, X. Zhou, H. Chen, G. Zou, *CrystEngComm* **2011**, *13*, 2871–2877.
- [26] S. Y. Ng, A. H. W. Ngan, *Electrochim. Acta* **2011**, *56*, 7686–7695.
- [27] P. C. M. Laan, F. J. de Zwart, E. M. Wilson, A. Troglia, O. C. M. Lugier, N. J. Geels, R. Bliem, J. N. H. Reek, B. de Bruin, G. Rothenberg, N. Yan, *ACS Catal.* **2023**, *13*, 8467–8476.
- [28] V. Vedharathnam, G. G. Botte, *Electrochim. Acta* **2012**, *81*, 292–300.

- [29] W. Jud, C. A. Salazar, J. Imbrogno, J. Verghese, S. M. Guinness, J.-N. Desrosiers, C. O. Kappe, D. Cantillo, *Org. Process Res. Dev.* **2022**, *26*, 1486–1495.
- [30] R. M. A. Hameed, K. M. El-Khatib, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2010**, *35*, 2517–2529.
- [31] A. F. B. Barbosa, V. L. Oliveira, J. van Druenen, G. Tremiliosi-Filho, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **2015**, *746*, 31–38.
- [32] A. A. El-Shafei, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **1999**, *471*, 89–95.
- [33] W. M. Haynes, *CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, 95th Edition*, CRC Press, **2014**.
- [34] D. S. Hall, C. Bock, B. R. MacDougall, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2013**, *160*, F235.
- [35] Y. F. Yuan, X. H. Xia, J. B. Wu, J. L. Yang, Y. B. Chen, S. Y. Guo, *Electrochim. Acta* **2011**, *56*, 2627–2632.
- [36] F. Malara, A. Minguzzi, M. Marelli, S. Morandi, R. Psaro, V. Dal Santo, A. Naldoni, *ACS Catal.* **2015**, *5*, 5292–5300.
- [37] A. C. Garcia, T. Touzalin, C. Nieuwland, N. Perini, M. T. M. Koper, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58*, 12999–13003.
- [38] O. Diaz-Morales, D. Ferrus-Suspedra, M. T. M. Koper, *Chem. Sci.* **2016**, *7*, 2639–2645.
- [39] S. Klaus, Y. Cai, M. W. Louie, L. Trotochaud, A. T. Bell, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2015**, *119*, 7243–7254.
- [40] D. S. Hall, D. J. Lockwood, C. Bock, B. R. MacDougall, *Proc. Roy. Soc. A* **2015**, *471*, 20140792.
- [41] J.-M. Ye, D.-H. He, F. Li, Y.-L. Li, J.-B. He, *Chem. Commun.* **2018**, *54*, 10116–10119.
- [42] T. Tian, H. Gao, X. Zhou, L. Zheng, J. Wu, K. Li, Y. Ding, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2018**, *3*, 2150–2158.
- [43] Y. Zhou, N. López, *ACS Catal.* **2020**, *10*, 6254–6261.
- [44] C. M. Stern, D. W. Hayes, L. O. Kgoadi, N. Elgrishi, *Environ. Sci.* **2020**, *6*, 1256–1261.
- [45] P. Meshram, U. Prakash, L. Bhagat, Abhilash, H. Zhao, E. D. van Hullebusch, *Minerals* **2020**, *10*, 290.
- [46] B. Beverskog, I. Puigdomenech, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **1997**, *144*, 3476.
- [47] Y. Wu, M.-J. Zhao, F. Li, J. Xie, Y. Li, J.-B. He, *Langmuir* **2020**, *36*, 5126–5133.
- [48] A. Soundarya Mary, C. Murugan, D. Mahendiran, P. Murugan, A. Pandikumar, *Mater. Today* **2024**, *41*, 101541.
- [49] Y. Dou, C.-T. He, L. Zhang, M. Al-Mamun, H. Guo, W. Zhang, Q. Xia, J. Xu, L. Jiang, Y. Wang, P. Liu, X.-M. Chen, H. Yin, H. Zhao, *Cell Rep.* **2020**, *1*, 100077.
- [50] R. A. Marquez, E. Kalokowski, M. Espinosa, J. T. Bender, Y. Jun Son, K. Kawashima, C. E. Chukwunke, L. A. Smith, H. Celio, A. Dolocan, X. Zhan, N. Miller, D. J. Milliron, J. Resasco, C. Buddie Mullins, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2024**, *17*, 2028–2045.
- [51] M. W. Louie, A. T. Bell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 12329–12337.
- [52] P. Yan, Q. Liu, H. Zhang, L. Qiu, H. Bin Wu, X.-Y. Yu, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2021**, *9*, 15586–15594.
- [53] I. Spanos, J. Masa, A. Zeradjanin, R. Schlögl, *Catal. Lett.* **2021**, *151*, 1843–1856.
- [54] O. van der Heijden, S. Park, J. J. J. Eggebeen, M. T. M. Koper, *Angew. Chem.* **2023**, *135*, e202216477.
- [55] N. Elgrishi, K. J. Rountree, B. D. McCarthy, E. S. Rountree, T. T. Eisenhart, J. L. Dempsey, *J. Chem. Educ.* **2018**, *95*, 197–206.

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

We examine the effect of metal impurities on nickel foam electrodes by electrodepositing Cu, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co and Ni on nickel foam and studying them in OER. Using a variety of methods, we show that even small amounts of impurities can have large effects. This highlights the importance of impurities for electrode design and large-scale application.

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The Influence of Metal Impurities on NiOOH Electrocatalytic Activity in the Oxygen Evolution Reaction

